

FOREST4EU partner: BOSCAT

OG: Calor Rural

OG's country: Spain

Type of Innovation: Social Innovation

Innovation in products, processes and marketing to introduce local woods with special, greater value-added characteristics to the Catalan market

Introduction

The aim of the project is to valorise wood with special dimensions and characteristics in the forests of Catalonia, and in particular, wood produced by the members of the cooperative Forestal de Catalunya, SCCL (Serveis Forestals, SF) and the company Agrupació Forestal del Montnegre i el Corredor SL (AFMC) through innovation in products, the transformation process and the methods/techniques for marketing these types of wood, presenting them to the market in a format that is different from the usual format in Catalonia. The project aims to introduce a new product "as a different concept to the formats of planks in standard dimensions available in large retail outlets," and to offer a product that has been preprocessed as little as possible and dried under ideal conditions to ensure an optimal technological quality and in "boules", using the French model. The idea is to introduce this product to the retail market (wood craftsmen, cabinetmakers, carpenters, decorators, architects, surveyors, etc.), which has been identified as a "market niche". The aim is to improve the economic results of forestry operations and provide the opportunity for forest owners to have a wider range with greater added value when selling their wood, in a market different from the one for which this wood was initially intended, which was packaging and/or bioenergy. Another objective of the project is to improve the competitiveness of the two groups of forest producers (Forestal de Catalunya, SCCL and Agrupació Forestal del Montnegre Corredor), which include forestry producers and groups of forest owners. By applying new processes, they can add value to their products, and focus them on new local markets, with short distribution circuits.

Lessons learned

The end result is the "SingularWood" business initiative, which aims to facilitate marketing and add value to the woods from Catalonia's forests with special and unique features. Each and every one of our products is unique. The virtual platform (www.singularwood.cat) has been created to offer all the "boules" to the end customers: cabinetmakers, carpenters, designers, etc. The same platform contains a description of each product, which includes all the necessary information and which asks the craftsman who will use the "boules" to determine the suitability of each product for the creation of the unique pieces that they have conceived and designed. The execution of this OG led to the launch of an initiative that gives added value to trunks

with unique features, and which after going through a minimal pre-treatment process and with a guarantee of traceability, can be made available to craftsmen (cabinetmakers, carpenters, designers, architects, etc.) for use in their unique creations.

For further information contact

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Pictures

Figure 1: “Wood product (1)”

Figure 2: “Wood product (2)”

Figure 3: “Wood product (3)”

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://singularwood.cat/>

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